

RUBATO: A Multi-Version Benchmark for Robust Music Analysis and Transcription

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Abstract

1 Robustness is a fundamental challenge for deep
2 learning, as models frequently inherit dataset bi-
3 ases and fail to generalize across real-world vari-
4 ability. Models for music audio analysis and
5 transcription—machine-learning tasks of particular
6 difficulty and data scarcity—often lack robustness
7 to changes in instrumentation, interpretation, or
8 recording conditions. In contrast to text and vision,
9 robustness in music remains underexplored. To ad-
10 dress this gap, we introduce RUBATO, a manually
11 curated, fully open music dataset and benchmark.
12 Our central idea is to exploit the unique oppor-
13 tunities of Western classical music, for which we
14 find famous works free of copyright and an abun-
15 dance of available recordings that follow the same
16 score but differ in interpretation and recording con-
17 ditions. For RUBATO, we collected and recorded
18 14 canonical works in up to 60 versions, totaling
19 566 audio tracks and 42 hours of audio, including
20 original recordings, arrangements (for different in-
21 strumentations), adaptations, controlled piano ren-
22 derings, and synthesized versions. We further cu-
23 rated symbolic scores and expert annotations for
24 various tasks. Ensuring structural coherence, we
25 transfer annotations between versions using state-
26 of-the-art alignment techniques, which we evaluate
27 for the heterogeneous version pairs in RUBATO.
28 The resulting high-quality annotations allow for
29 benchmarking music analysis models, which we
30 demonstrate for two selected tasks—automatic mu-
31 sic transcription and local key estimation. Going
32 beyond standard metrics, the multi-version design
33 of RUBATO enables systematic evaluation not only
34 of models’ efficacy but also of their consistency
35 across versions of the same work. This notion, for-
36 malized as cross-version consistency, allows us to
37 assess a model’s robustness along various dimen-
38 sions. In our experiments, we find that most sys-
39 tems struggle to generalize under real-world vari-
40 ability, highlighting the need for more robust mod-
41 els and for benchmarks such as RUBATO that are
42 capable of measuring such robustness.

1 Introduction

Analog to the *visual* domain [Hendrycks and Dietterich, 2019], the human *auditory* system is robust in ways that current music analysis systems are not. Humans can interpret and understand music across a range of acoustic variations, being able to abstract from instrumentation, interpretation, and recording conditions. In contrast, DL systems applied to music, frequently fail to generalize across datasets and domains. For instance, piano transcription systems that perform well on the MAESTRO dataset show significant efficacy drops on datasets recorded under different conditions, such as MAPS [Edwards *et al.*, 2025]. Moreover, state-of-the-art models for multi-instrument transcription suffer from severe degradation in efficacy when tested on unseen datasets [Chang *et al.*, 2024; Gardner *et al.*, 2022].

This highlights a broader issue: Current evaluation strategies rely on small or homogeneous datasets, which introduce biases in terms of instrumentation or recording conditions, among others. Without thoroughly evaluating robustness, it is hard to understand technical advances and to identify effective methods. This issue is critical for applications in musicology, where biased model predictions can lead to incorrect conclusions. While robustness is a well-studied topic for DL in vision [Hendrycks *et al.*, 2021] and text [Niven and Kao, 2019; Elazar *et al.*, 2021], it remains underexplored for DL algorithms applied to music. This is partly due to the limitations of existing datasets, which often focus on a single instrument as the piano in MAESTRO [Hawthorne *et al.*, 2019] and MAPS [Emiya *et al.*, 2010] or the guitar in GuitarSet [Xi *et al.*, 2018] and GAPS [Riley *et al.*, 2024]), on a single composer or work cycle such as SWD [Weiß *et al.*, 2021], BPSD [Zeitler *et al.*, 2024], or WRD [Weiß *et al.*, 2023]. Others only partially support open audio data (SWD, BPSD & WRD) or are not public as a whole as RWC [Goto *et al.*, 2003], have only synthesized audio as Slakh [Manilow *et al.*, 2019], or as MusicNet ([Thickstun *et al.*, 2017], lack high-quality annotations and instrument balance [Gardner *et al.*, 2022; Weiß and Peeters, 2022].

To address these issues, we introduce RUBATO¹, a man-

¹RobUstness Benchmark for music Analysis and TranscriptiOn. *Tempo rubato* (Italian for “stolen time”) is an expressive tool that refers to the idea of “borrowing time” from one section of music and giving it to another.

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Figure 1: RUBATO dataset. For 14 famous works (green, see Table 1), we collected many heterogeneous versions (blue, see Table 3), including original versions (OV) in differing recording quality, arrangements (AR) for other instruments, systematic piano renderings (SR) in different recording setups, and synthesized versions (SY)—all structurally coherent and carefully aligned to a shared musical time axis (red). We also provide adaptations (AD, not in figure) that diverge structurally but rely on the same works.

82 ually curated dataset² and benchmark³ with an emphasis on
 83 heterogeneity in quality, interpretation, and instrumentation
 84 (see Figure 1). Beyond being a new resource for the data-
 85 scarce music audio field, RUBATO unites the advantages of
 86 several existing datasets: It goes beyond the piano solo sce-
 87 nario and (as MusicNet but other than SWD, BPSD, WRD)
 88 features fully open audio data. As SWD, BPSD & WRD, it
 89 is a score-based multi-version dataset with high-quality mu-
 90 sical annotations. In contrast to those, it is balanced across
 91 composers and work characteristics and comprises an exten-
 92 sive amount (up to 60) heterogeneous versions. As in BPSD
 93 and SWD, the majority of versions in RUBATO exhibit a co-
 94 herent structure. Going beyond all those, RUBATO combines
 95 original recordings, arrangements, systematic renderings, and
 96 synthesized audio for each work, allowing for the systematic
 97 evaluation of robustness.

98 As our main contributions, we (1) selected 14 famous
 99 works across 150 years of music history, featuring 12 com-
 100 posers and being roughly balanced in tempo, mode (ma-
 101 jor/minor keys), and instrumentation. Following the idea of
 102 [Thickstun *et al.*, 2017], we (2) collected public domain and
 103 creative commons material (scores and recordings). More-
 104 over, we recorded (3) several own performances in a profes-
 105 sional studio, (4) systematic versions (MIDI reproduction pi-
 106 ano renderings) in a controlled acoustic environment using
 107 different setups and device qualities, including video cap-
 108 ture of the reproduction piano, and (5) synthesized versions
 109 with two professional sample libraries. We (6) ensured struc-
 110 tural coherence across most (90%) versions and (7) created
 111 high-quality musical annotations of note events, beats, mea-
 112 sures, structure, instrumentation, local and global keys. We
 113 (8) tested different strategies of score–audio and audio–audio
 114 alignment and (9) performed alignment with best settings to

transfer annotations between score and different audio ver- 115
 sions, obtaining a shared musical time axis. 116

Beyond the dataset, we (10) propose the RUBATO bench- 117
 mark, a strategy to utilize our resource as an unseen dataset 118
 for systematically evaluating music analysis and transcription 119
 models. Going beyond standard evaluation metrics, we pro- 120
 pose to measure cross-version consistency of model predic- 121
 tions as an indicator for their robustness [Venohr *et al.*, 2025; 122
 Ding *et al.*, 2025]. We (11) extend these consistency mea- 123
 sures with two variants that measure consistency of evalua- 124
 tion metrics instead of predictions. We (12) utilize these 125
 metrics for selected pairings of versions to measure robust- 126
 ness against specific, particularly difficult distribution shifts 127
 (e. g., from piano to other instruments or from synthesized to 128
 real audio recordings). With this strategy, we (13) compare 129
 several existing models for Automatic Music Transcription 130
 (AMT) and Local Key Estimation (LKE) and conclude on 131
 their robustness under real-world variability of music data. 132

2 Related Work 133

To situate our research within existing literature, we summa- 134
 rize prior work on robustness and multi-version data. We 135
 already discussed selected music datasets in Section 1. 136

Robustness: DL models are known to exploit shortcuts 137
 and inherit biases from their training data [Geirhos *et al.*, 138
 2020]. In other domains, several datasets have been pro- 139
 posed to benchmark model robustness to distribution shifts, 140
 including ImageNet-C/P [Hendrycks and Dietterich, 2019], 141
 Imagenet-R [Hendrycks *et al.*, 2021], WILDS [Koh *et al.*, 142
 2021], or ARES [Liu *et al.*, 2025]. Such distribution shifts 143
 can be categorized as natural or synthetic and evaluated un- 144
 der worst-case scenarios, as in adversarial robustness [Good- 145
 fellow *et al.*, 2015], or under average-case scenarios, such 146
 as corruption robustness [Hendrycks and Dietterich, 2019]. 147
 As adversarial threats are considered less problematic in mu- 148

²<https://zenodo.org/records/18302105>

³<https://anonymous.4open.science/r/rubato-benchmark-E635>

Table 1: Overview of the 14 works included in the RUBATO dataset sorted by composition year. In total, the dataset contains 42 hours of audio. * For `Pict-10`, we provide `SR` and `SY` both for the piano original and Ravel’s orchestra version.

Work ID	Composer ID	Title	Year	Orig. Instr.	Key	Number of Versions				
						OV	AR	AD	SR/SY	Total
BWV1007-01	Bach	Cello Suite Nr.1 in G-Dur BWV1007, 1. Prélude	1724	Cello	G:maj	15	7	2	6	30
RV269-01	Vivaldi	Le quattro stagioni: La Primavera, 1. Allegro	1725	Strings	E:maj	16	18	0	6	40
HWV040-1-01	Handel	Serse HWV040, Ombra mai fù	1738	Voice, Strings	F:maj	4	38	12	6	60
HWV056-2-44	Handel	Messiah, Hallelujah	1767	Choir, Orchestra	D:maj	12	12	6	6	36
G275-03	Boccherini	Quintetto d’archi G275, 3. Minuetto	1775	Strings	A:maj	19	10	5	6	40
Op047-01	Beethoven	Violinsonate Nr. 9 in A-Dur (Kreutzer) Op.047, 1. Adagio	1805	Violin, Piano	A:min	28	0	2	6	36
KV618	Mozart	Ave Verum Corpus KV618	1807	Choir, Strings, Organ	D:maj	12	13	9	6	40
D733-01	Schubert	Trois Marches Militaires D733, 1. Allegro vivace	1826	Piano	D:maj	4	25	8	6	43
Op072-0	Beethoven	Fidelio Op.072, Overtüre	1826	Orchestra	E:maj	37	0	0	6	43
Op039-05	SchumannR	Liederkreis Op.039, 5. Mondnacht	1842	Voice, Piano	E:maj	39	2	0	6	47
Nabucco-12	Verdi	Nabucco, Va pensiero sull’ali dorate	1842	Choir, Orchestra	F#:maj	25	1	6	6	38
H048-04	Berlioz	Symphonie fantastique H048, 4. Marche au supplice	1845	Orchestra	G:min	33	0	0	6	39
Pict-10	Mussorgsky	Pictures at an Exhibition, 10. The Great Gate of Kiev	1886	Piano	Eb:Maj	13	21	6	12*	52
Op115-01	Brahms	Klarinettenquintett h-Moll Op. 115, 1. Allegro	1892	Clarinet, Strings	B:min	16	0	0	6	22
						273	147	56	90	566

149 sic analysis, we restrict our scope to robustness against *natural*
150 *ly occurring, non-adversarial distribution shifts*. While
151 this does not cover all aspects of robustness, it addresses
152 the most central and practically relevant challenges for music
153 analysis models in real-world applications.

154 **Leveraging multi-version data:** To study robustness in
155 music analysis and transcription, [Weiß *et al.*, 2020] and
156 [Weiß and Peeters, 2022] leveraged multi-version datasets
157 by analyzing the impact of different splitting strategies. For
158 domain adaption, [Liu and Weiß, 2024] used multi-version
159 datasets within a teacher–student learning paradigm by using
160 CVC to filter training labels. [Venohr *et al.*, 2025] and [Ding
161 *et al.*, 2025] formalized local prediction consistency (see Sec-
162 tion 4.1) and systematically explore it for the tasks of Multi-
163 Pitch Estimation (MPE) and LKE, respectively. Those works
164 showed consistency not only to be a proxy for model *efficacy*
165 but also to provide insight into model *robustness*.

166 3 RUBATO Dataset

167 Motivated by the limitations of existing datasets, we created
168 RUBATO as a heterogeneous, fully open music dataset with
169 high-quality annotations. We now describe its structure and
170 content regarding works and versions (Section 3.1), temporal
171 alignment (Section 3.2), and annotations (Section 3.3).

172 3.1 Musical Works and Versions

173 A unique property of Western classical music is the abun-
174 dant of recordings that follow a shared musical score while
175 differing in interpretation, instrumentation, and recording
176 conditions. This makes it a well-suited testbed for systemat-
177 ically studying robustness in music analysis models. Guided
178 by this observation, our primary design principle was to con-
179 struct a fully open-source dataset that maximizes the number
180 of available recordings per work. To this end, we considered
181 12 famous composers from the common-practice period (18th
182 and 19th century, free of copyright) and selected 14 popular
183 works (see Table 1) for which a large number of recordings
184 are publicly available. At the same time, we strived for bal-
185 ance in composition years (1724–1892), instrumentation (vo-
186 cal/instrumental, choir/solo voice, orchestra/chamber mu-
187 sic, with/without piano, see Table 2), keys and modes (ma-

Table 2: Track-wise instrumentation of all OV, AR, and AD versions.

Instrumentation	# Tracks	hh:mm
Orchestra	114	9:35
Violin, Piano	33	5:47
Choir, Orchestra	43	3:11
Clarinet, Strings	16	2:32
Voice, Piano	41	2:28
Solo Piano	30	2:02
Strings	39	1:57
Voice, Strings	20	1:04
Strings, Harpsichord	14	0:50
Choir, Organ	12	0:45
Choir, Strings, Organ	11	0:41
Solo Cello	15	0:37
Solo Organ	8	0:28
Other	74	3:48

188 jor/minor), as well as tempi. All remaining biases are results
189 of our design decision for maximizing version depth and re-
190 flect the availability of recordings within the repertoire.⁴
191

192 For each of the 14 works, we collected musical scores
193 in different formats and between 22–60 audio versions
194 per work, which we categorize into six version types
195 (see Table 3) differing in performance style, improvisa-
196 tion, and degree of fidelity to the original score. Follow-
197 ing [Weiß *et al.*, 2021], we name all files consistently:
198 *ComposerID_WorkID_VersionType-VersionID.ext*, for exam-
199 ple `Boccherini_G275-03_OV-Krux2022.wav`, with
200 the version left out for score-related data. We now describe
201 our version types in detail (see Table 3 for an overview).
202

203 **Score versions:** We collected open-source scores, applied
204 optical music recognition if necessary, corrected the machine-
205 readable scores in MuseScore (an open source editor), and
206 adapted them according to scholarly-critical editions. Along
207 with MuseScore files, we exported image, PDF, MusicXML,
and MIDI versions, the latter serving for generating note-level
annotations and for rendering systematic piano recordings.

⁴Please note that RUBATO serves to evaluate and improve *tech-*
nical methods for music analysis, for which cultural and gender bi-
ases are not expected to be relevant. The resulting methods can then
be used for *musicological* studies addressing such biases by deliber-
ately considering female and non-white composers as well as non-
Western musical cultures. Accordingly, we prioritized acoustic and
musical diversity over diversity of creators.

Table 3: Version types in the RUBATO dataset. Possible **tasks** include AMT (1), beat tracking (2), LKE (3), pitch class activity (4), chord (5, will be added), structure analysis (6), instrument detection (7), global key estimation (8) and version retrieval (9).

Version Type	Struct.	Pitch	Instr.	Alignment	Tasks	hh:mm
Orig. Ref. Version (OV-R)	✓	✓	✓	manual	1-9	24:07
Orig. Version (OV)	✓	✓	✓	transferred		
Ref. Arrangement (AR-R)	✓	(✓)	✗	manual	3-9	8:38
Arrangement (AR)	✓	(✓)	✗	transferred		
Adaptation (AD-S)	✗	(✓)	✓	-	7-9	3:23
Adaptations (AD)	✗	(✓)	✗	-		
Systematic Rendition (SR)	✓	✓	✗	exact	1-9	4:29 2:16
Synthesized (SY)	✓	✓	✓	exact		
						42:55

Figure 2: MIDI-controllable reproduction piano (Yamaha C3X Ensfire Pro) in the acoustically optimized studio with different microphone setups.

Real-world audio versions: To stick with open audio material, we manually collected professional recordings, which are in the Public Domain⁵ or released under Creative Commons licenses. In addition, we record additional versions of four works including *Brahms_Op115-01*, all featuring conservatory students and graduates as performers. Our different audio versions include the following types:

- *Original Versions* (OV) exactly follow the score in terms of instrumentation and structure, thus containing the exact same note events up to temporal variations. One challenge are structural differences between versions such as repetitions played in some and omitted in other versions. Following [Zeitler *et al.*, 2024], we manually edit recordings deviating from our reference original (OV-R) to ensure structural coherence. Additionally, we annotate all transpositions and octave shifts of vocal soloists (occurring when comparing female and male voices).
- *Arrangements* (AR) preserve the overall structure and harmony but may differ in instrumentation and exact pitch content, especially octave/register of notes (e.g., a guitar version of the *Cello Suite*). For *Mussorgsky_Pict-10*, along with the 13 original piano versions, we have 21 orchestral arrangements following M. Ravel’s orchestral version.
- *Adaptations* (AD) may significantly deviate from the original either in structure (AD-S) or in both structure and instrumentation (AD) while the original work remains recognizable. This category includes unique renditions such as a barrel-organ version of *Verdi_Nabucco-12*. These versions can be used for global tasks, such as version retrieval or global key estimation.

Controlled audio versions: In addition, we created controlled versions to serve as a standardized reference across all works, to ensure comparability between works, and to enable investigation of particular domain shifts (such as between piano–orchestra or synthesized–real audio):

- *Systematic Renderings* (SR) of all works with a MIDI-controllable Yamaha C3X ENSPIRE PRO grand piano

⁵Under EU law, performances recorded before 1963 are in the Public Domain, which we used as basis for inclusion. Please note that these recordings might not be in the Public Domain in countries outside the EU.

were recorded in an acoustically optimized studio (Figure 2). We used multiple microphone setups for comparability: close-miking and room-miking (both with Schoeps MK5 microphones), as well as a consumer-grade handheld stereo recorder (Zoom H4n) to account for lower-quality conditions. From the original score (e. g., for orchestra), we extract a MIDI file, map all note events to one channel, and clean up notes events (merging duplicates, splitting overlapping events). We captured recordings via a Yamaha DM3 digital mixing desk using Nuendo software, both with and without reverb.

- *Synthesized Versions* (SY) were rendered from the symbolic scores using two high-quality sampling libraries: East West Symphonic Orchestra (EWSO) and Steinberg HALion Symphonic Orchestra (HSO).

We provide all recordings as mono WAV files at 22.05 kHz sampling rate to be used for research purposes.

Other Versions: In addition to the audio versions, we also include synchronized video recordings of SR capturing the automatically moving piano keys, which can be used, e. g., for the task of visual piano transcription [Koepke *et al.*, 2020].

3.2 Cross-Version Alignment Strategy

Different versions of a work generally follow the same score regarding pitch information (note sequence), but have large freedom in shaping global and local tempo, including fluctuations such as agogics, ritardando, or rubato. To align the physical timelines across all versions and with the musical timeline of the score, we employ a multi-stage synchronization approach inspired by prior work [Weiß *et al.*, 2021; Weiß *et al.*, 2023; Zeitler *et al.*, 2024].

Manual annotations: For each work, we selected two reference versions, one original (OV-R) and one arrangement (AR-R). For these versions, we manually annotated downbeat (measure) positions (for OV-R also beat positions) using Sonic Visualizer [Cannam *et al.*, 2010].

Annotation transfer: We then used audio–audio synchronization to transfer the manual annotations to all other OV/AR versions. The transferred beat annotations serve as anchor points for a subsequent fine-grained score–audio alignment. This step aligns the score’s musical timeline with each version’s physical timeline, enabling precise transfer of note events and other annotations.

Figure 3: Correctly aligned measure positions within a given tolerance averaged over manually annotated versions.

Alignment quality: For synchronization, we used the SyncToolbox [Müller *et al.*, 2021] implementation of memory-restricted multi-scale dynamic time warping (MrMsDTW) [Prätzlich *et al.*, 2016]. While the signal processing (SP) features of the SyncToolbox are known to obtain high quality for audio–audio synchronization (especially for piano), our heterogeneous pairings (score–audio, synthesized–real, piano–orchestra, high–low quality) may pose challenges. To assess the quality of our alignment in these scenarios, we conducted an in-depth study using our manual measure annotations (for OV–R/AR–R) and systematic versions (SR, SY), where we obtain measure annotations from the source MIDI file. We compared various SP features as used by [Müller *et al.*, 2021] with DL-based pitch and chroma features derived from a MPE model [Weiß and Peeters, 2022]. From this experiment, we found that DL-based chroma features, especially in combination with SP-based onset features, achieve higher accuracy than other features such as SP-based chroma or pitch features. Based on these findings, we adopted this hybrid feature approach (DL-based pitch class features combined with SP-based chroma onset estimates) with a frame rate of 43.07 Hz.

Figure 3 shows accuracy curves using these features for various heterogeneous pairings. The alignment of SR versions to other piano versions, a homogeneous scenario, is the most accurate (AUC = 0.84). Our primary scenarios for this dataset (score–audio and audio–audio with different recording quality), still work well despite considerable heterogeneity of the data. To contextualize the accuracy of our alignment, we need to relate the values to human inter-annotator deviations, which have been shown to be in the order of 100 ms and higher for complex classical works such as romantic operas [Weiß *et al.*, 2016]. At this 100 ms tolerance, we achieve over 80% in heterogeneous and up to 95% in homogeneous cases. For the quality of the resulting annotations, these curves rather indicate lower bounds since we use additional anchor points (from manual measure and beat positions) to support the annotation transfer. For the reference versions OV–R and AR–R (manually annotated), the quality is naturally even higher, and the MIDI-based SY and SR versions have perfect annotations derived from the score.

3.3 Musical Annotations

RUBATO provides various expert-created annotations, which may serve to evaluate and improve a range of music analysis tasks (see Table 3). As described above, we obtain beat and

measure annotations for all version. Based on the score, we manually create structure and local key annotations. Relying on our measure positions and alignments (see Section 3.2), we transfer these annotations to all versions (excluding AD). Similarly, we derive note-level annotations (including instrument labels) for all OV versions. We further provide track-wise annotations such as global key and structure.

4 RUBATO Benchmark

Like any dataset, RUBATO can be split for train–test experiments. For this case, we propose a best-practice split strategy together with the dataset. However, we primarily conceive RUBATO as an unseen benchmark, designed to expose robustness gaps in music analysis systems and, therefore, recommend it to be used as a *hold-out test set*. What makes RUBATO distinctive is its structure and its heterogeneity: for each work, multiple aligned audio versions are available, differing in performers, instrumentation, and recording conditions. This diversity makes RUBATO not only a challenging benchmark, but also uniquely suited for studying aspects of robustness. In particular, it allows us to ask:

How consistent are model predictions across different versions of the same work, i. e., when musicians, instruments, or recording conditions change?

To address this, we introduce a set of diagnostic research tools supplementing standard metrics (Section 4.1) and exemplify their usage on AMT (Section 4.2) and LKE (Section 4.3).

4.1 Cross-Version Consistency

Existing evaluation metrics measure how *well* models analyze or transcribe individual recordings, but fail to capture whether model predictions are *robust*, i. e., remain stable under domain shifts. For instance, AMT systems often successfully transcribe some versions of a work but fail on others, even though the underlying musical content is identical (e. g., Figure 4b). For application fields such as musicology, such inconsistencies are problematic. Comparative studies like corpus analysis require model robustness to performer, instrument, and recording changes. To explicitly measure this robustness, we consider Cross-Version Consistency (CVC) as proposed in [Ding *et al.*, 2025; Venohr *et al.*, 2025].

We define three variants of CVC: **Global Evaluation Consistency (GEC)** measures how much track-wise model efficacy differs between versions of a work. Visually, this corresponds to the average pairwise vertical proximity per work in Figure 4. **Local Evaluation Consistency (LEC)** goes beyond GEC as it considers *when* errors occur by locally comparing efficacy at corresponding frames. **Local Prediction Consistency (LPC)** goes beyond LEC as it captures *which* predictions are made by directly comparing model output at corresponding frames. As LPC is annotation-free, it is particularly relevant for tasks where annotations can be ambiguous (e. g. LKE) or imprecise and tedious to create (e. g. AMT).

Version pairs: Let each audio track $X_{w,v}$ be uniquely defined by a work w and a version v . We define the set of all cross-version pairs as $\mathcal{P} = \{(X_{w_1,v_1}, X_{w_2,v_2}) \mid w_1 = w_2, v_1 \neq v_2\}$. Let $(X_{w_1}, X_{w_2}) \in \mathcal{P}$ be a cross-version pair and $Y_1, \hat{Y}_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times B}$ and $Y_2, \hat{Y}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times B}$ their respective

389 musical annotations and model predictions, with B being the
 390 number of output dimensions (e.g. 88 pitch bins for MPE
 391 or 24 key classes for LKE) and N and M being the number
 392 of time frames at a given frame rate. We compute CVC for
 393 individual pairs and then average over \mathcal{P} or certain subsets.

394 **Global comparison:** Given a global evaluation measure
 395 $g: \mathbb{R}^{N \times B} \times \mathbb{R}^{N \times B} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ we define $\mathbf{GEC} \in [0, 1]$ as

$$1 - |g(\hat{Y}_1, Y_1) - g(\hat{Y}_2, Y_2)|. \quad (1)$$

396 **Local comparison:** Since all version pairs share a common
 397 musical time axis, we can define musically meaningful local
 398 comparisons. Based on beat annotations (Section 3.2),
 399 we derive a warping path $P = (p(1), \dots, p(L))$, $p(l) =$
 400 $(n_l, m_l) \in [1 : N] \times [1 : M]$ with $L \geq \max(N, M)$, which
 401 establishes correspondences between time frames of two se-
 402 quences of lengths N and M . Given a local evaluation mea-
 403 sure $e: \mathbb{R}^B \times \mathbb{R}^B \rightarrow [0, 1]$, we define $\mathbf{LEC} \in [0, 1]$ as

$$1 - \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L |e(\hat{Y}_1(n_l), Y_1(n_l)) - e(\hat{Y}_2(m_l), Y_2(m_l))|. \quad (2)$$

404 Given a local similarity measure $s: \mathbb{R}^B \times \mathbb{R}^B \rightarrow [0, 1]$, we
 405 define $\mathbf{LPC} \in [0, 1]$ as

$$\frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L s(\hat{Y}_1(n_l), \hat{Y}_2(m_l)). \quad (3)$$

406 As some versions are performed in different keys, we trans-
 407 pose \hat{Y} accordingly before computing the similarity.

408 **Aspects of Consistency:** To gain nuanced insights into dif-
 409 ferent aspects of robustness, we define subsets of \mathcal{P} to make
 410 certain domain shifts explicit. ‘‘Piano–Other’’ measures CVC
 411 on all version pairs of SR and OV and, thus, captures the shift
 412 from rendered piano recordings to real-world recordings of
 413 various instrumentations. ‘‘Synth–Real’’ aggregates CVC be-
 414 tween all pairs of SY and OV, thus capturing the shift from
 415 synthesized renderings to real-world recordings.

416 **Trivial Solution:** While, by definition, a model making
 417 constant but incorrect predictions (e.g., predicting the same
 418 pitch for every frame) yields a high CVC score, we note that
 419 this does not invalidate the metric since we consider CVC as
 420 an *additional figure of merit* rather than a standalone metric.

4.2 Experiment 1: Automatic Music Transcription

422 We now want to demonstrate the usage of our benchmark by
 423 exemplarily applying it to two selected tasks. In the first ex-
 424 periment, we evaluate several multi-instrument AMT models
 425 for their efficacy and CVC on RUBATO.

426 **Evaluation:** We assess model efficacy using both note-
 427 level and frame-level metrics. At the note level, we re-
 428 port F_{On}^{Δ} , a pitch–onset F-measure that takes a note as cor-
 429 rect if its pitch is within a quarter tone and its onset within
 430 $\pm \Delta$ ms of the reference. We also report a pitch-wise on-
 431 set/offset measure $F_{\text{On+Off}}^{\Delta}$, which further requires the offset
 432 to be within $\pm \Delta$ ms or 20% of the reference note’s duration.
 433 We match reference and predicted notes using `mir_eval`
 434 [Raffel *et al.*, 2014]. Since annotation accuracy is lower in
 435 multi-instrument scenarios (see Section 3.2), we set $\Delta = 100$
 436 ms. At the frame level, we compute Precision (P), Recall (R),
 437 and F-measure by comparing binary piano-roll representa-
 438 tions of predictions and targets in $\{0, 1\}^{N \times 72}$ at a frame

Figure 4: Frame-level evaluation for for MT3 and ResNet. For both models, controlled piano versions (SR, red) mostly act as an upper bound and are easiest to transcribe. F-measure decreases for synthesized versions with the original instrumentation (SY, green) and further for (noisy) real-world recordings (OV, grey). However, the differences are larger for MT3, with some versions failing entirely.

439 rate of 43.07 Hz. For models with probabilistic outputs, we
 440 additionally report Average Precision (AP). For CVC, we bi-
 441 naryze outputs and choose F-measure as metric for e , g , and
 442 s . By definition, we evaluate CVC on the frame-level.

443 **Models:** We evaluate several pre-trained models designed
 444 for frame-level, note-level, or hybrid transcription. For
 445 frame-level AMT, we use a medium-sized ResNet [Weiß
 446 and Peeters, 2022], trained on other classical music multi-
 447 version datasets as described by [Venohr *et al.*, 2025]. For
 448 hybrid models, we test the Notes and Multipitch (NMP)
 449 model [Bittner *et al.*, 2022], referred to as Basic Pitch (BP)
 450 and a custom trained checkpoint for [Maman and Bermano,
 451 2022], which uses an enlarged version of the Onsets and
 452 Frames architecture [Hawthorne *et al.*, 2018] (NoteEM). We
 453 evaluate both their frame-level output before decoding (–Fr)
 454 and note note-level output after decoding (–No). For pure
 455 note-level models, we consider ReconVat [Cheuk *et al.*,
 456 2021], trained in a semi-supervised fashion, as well as two
 457 Transformer-based models that directly output note events:
 458 MT3 [Gardner *et al.*, 2022] and YMT3+ [Chang *et al.*, 2024].

459 **Results:** Table 4 shows that note-level transcription re-
 460 mains highly challenging in the multi-instrument setting of
 461 RUBATO. Even F_{On}^{100} , assuming higher onset tolerance and
 462 ignored offsets, the best is only $F=56.7$ (MT3). While
 463 NoteEM–No and MT3 are comparable regarding standard
 464 metrics, NoteEM–No shows higher CVC across all pairs and
 465 metrics. A possible explanation is that the inductive bias of
 466 CNNs increases robustness, although more controlled exper-
 467 iments are needed to confirm this. Figure 4b and the Piano–
 468 Other CVC indicate a strong piano bias for MT3, which partly
 469 explains its lower consistency. While these findings are pre-
 470 liminary, they demonstrate that the RUBATO benchmark can
 471 provide additional information beyond standard metrics. In-
 472 terestingly, even though YMT3+—an adaptation of MT3—is

Table 4: RUBATO benchmark for two AMT tasks. Results for eight selected models.

Output	Model	Param.	Standard Metrics						Cross-Version Consistency Measures, Averaged								
			Note-Level		Frame-Level				All Pairs			Piano-Other			Synth-Real		
			$F_{\text{On+Off}}^{100}$	F_{On}^{100}	P	R	F	AP	GEC	LEC	LPC	GEC	LEC	LPC	GEC	LEC	LPC
Frame	ResNet	5M	-	-	78.5	65.7	70.2	78.4	94.3	77.5	63.3	91.7	74.4	56.3	91.7	75.5	62.5
	NoteEM-Fr	64M	-	-	67.2	66.0	65.8	68.3	88.4	72.4	54.7	81.2	67.8	51.8	80.6	68.9	53.7
	BP-Fr	17K	-	-	46.8	30.1	34.5	33.8	90.7	77.1	41.5	89.9	74.8	30.8	84.9	73.6	35.6
Note	NoteEM-No	64M	29.2	55.1	68.6	55.4	60.1	-	90.5	71.9	50.6	86.9	67.9	47.7	87.4	68.9	48.8
	BP-No	17K	22.4	44.8	75.4	46.7	54.1	-	85.2	70.8	45.2	81.1	66.8	41.4	78.5	66.7	45.6
	ReconVAT	61M	20.6	40.8	77.0	28.5	39.2	-	89.8	71.6	35.9	87.8	67.7	28.4	83.5	68.1	34.3
	MT3	60M	39.9	56.7	71.0	52.6	59.1	-	85.6	66.2	42.5	74.0	61.4	44.1	81.8	64.4	43.0
	YMT3+	46M	36.5	54.1	39.3	29.4	32.5	-	77.3	65.9	25.6	50.2	43.0	20.9	80.6	66.9	23.5

Table 5: Rubato benchmark for LKE. Results for two selected models.

Task	Model	Standard Metrics		Cross-Version Consistency Measures, Averaged								
		Recall	MIREX	All Pairs			Piano-Other			Synth-Real		
				GEC	LEC	LPC	GEC	LEC	LPC	GEC	LEC	LPC
LKE	CNN	66.7	73.5	93.3	82.1	70.7	92.4	80.3	71.4	92.7	81.8	72.4
	Octave-LSTM	79.7	85.2	93.2	88.8	85.4	91.9	86.6	83.0	93.7	89.2	85.1

comparable on the note-level, it is worse on the frame-level (F = 33). This is reflected in the consistencies, as they are defined on the frame level. Considering its small size, BP-No is competitive at both note and frame levels and also shows decent CVC. Among models with frame-level output, the comparatively small ResNet outperforms all others. Taken together, this suggests that high efficacy in multi-instrument AMT might not require very large models, and that current approaches may not be parameter-efficient. In summary, most models struggle to transcribe consistently under real-world variability, highlighting the need for more robust approaches.

4.3 Experiment 2: Local Key Estimation

As our second experiment, we demonstrate the RUBATO benchmark for LKE. As an essential component of harmony, LKE suffers from inherent musical ambiguity and high annotation subjectivity. [Weiß *et al.*, 2020] showed that inter-annotator agreement can be as low as 75%. However, current DL models often achieve recall rates above 80% when evaluated against a single annotation, suggesting overfitting to certain annotator styles. Therefore, [Ding *et al.*, 2025] proposed to use CVC (in the LPC variant) as an annotation-free evaluation strategy for LKE, avoiding the annotator bias. We follow this prior work and evaluate two models on RUBATO.

Evaluation: We evaluate models’ efficacy using two different standard metric for key estimation as implemented in the `mir_eval` library. The first one is key recall rate, which is the accuracy while ignoring frames annotated as “no key.” The second metric is MIREX score, which gives partial scores to fifth errors, relative errors, and parallel errors.

Models: We consider two baseline models from [Ding *et al.*, 2025]. The first one is a fully convolutional network (CNN), the second one is a CRNN with octave-based rearrangement (Octave-LSTM). We train the models on other cross-version datasets as in [Ding *et al.*, 2025].

Results: Figure 5 shows the key recall for Octave-LSTM. In contrast to AMT, results on different version types are similar for LKE, and using systematic rendering or synthesized data does not make LKE easier. The

Figure 5: Key recall per work for Octave-LSTM. Since AR versions keep harmonic content, we evaluate on these as well.

observations for CNN are similar. This suggests that for LKE, the challenge is less the variety of versions but to learn the *musical notion* of local key. Looking at the cross-version consistencies (Table 5), we find that Octave-LSTM achieves higher recall and MIREX score, and is also more consistent across different versions, with higher LEC and LPC values. We note that GEC does not correspond to efficacy—both models achieve similar GEC but Octave-LSTM obtains higher recall. Therefore, we argue that global consistencies alone as used by [Weiß *et al.*, 2020] are insufficient since models can make different mistakes in different versions, which may balance out globally. Thus, we consider local metrics (LEC/LPC) necessary to study model robustness.

5 Conclusions

With RUBATO, we contribute the first openly available, systematic multi-version dataset explicitly designed to study robustness in music analysis and transcription. Its 566 tracks comprising heterogeneous versions of 14 works from Western classical music span a wide range of instruments, performers, and recording conditions, thus offering a unique opportunity to benchmark ML model behavior within a challenging real-world scenario. Beyond the exemplary results shown in this paper, the RUBATO benchmark and the proposed consistency measures are a generic framework applicable to a variety of tasks such as beat, downbeat, or structure analysis, and we plan to enrich the dataset with further annotations soon.

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